

LIFE MANAGEMENT OF ADHESIVELY BONDED COMPOSITES STRUCTURES

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ABSTRACT

The damage tolerance certification approach (or “slow growth”) has been used to manage some metallic aircraft structures to enhance aircraft availability and reduce maintenance costs. To explore the possibility of this certification approach on composites, it is essential to build an understanding of the predictability of damage onset and progression of composite structures under static and fatigue loading. This work focuses on the development of experimental and modelling tools for life management of bonded composite joints with the ultimate goals of expanding damage limits and exploring feasibility of the damage tolerance certification approach. Damage onset and progression of a bonded structure with pre-existing damage under static loading was compared with that of a pristine one. Finite Element (FE) models were developed to predict performance of the bonded joints from damage onset to final failure. Pulsed thermography and a fibre optic sensing system were used to track damage onset and growth, and compared against FE results.

1 INTRODUCTION

Adhesively bonded composite joints are being used increasingly in aircraft structures due to their advantages of weight saving, uniform load transfer and being free of hole-drilling, as compared to mechanically fastened joints. Such weight saving is achieved by eliminating mechanical fasteners, and through achieving the same load transfer capability via thinner substrates. Adhesive bonding is being used not only on non-critical structures, but it is also being increasingly employed in primary structures in conjunction with mechanical fasteners to fulfil certification requirements [1-5].

There is a drive to explore certification approaches that allow for further reduction or elimination of fasteners by means of new design, advanced non-destructive inspection as well as bond strength proof testing. In addition, there has been an effort to investigate the potential of applying the damage tolerance (or “slow growth”) certification approach to composites management, in particular for composites airframe life extension. The slow growth approach has been proven effective for reducing aircraft downtime and costs associated with airframe maintenance since it uses a strategy that relies on damage growth prediction for inspection.

In order to identify how the damage tolerance certification approach may be applied on existing composite aircraft structures, as well as for new designs of future platforms, an understanding of composite damage onset and damage growth under static and fatigue loading is required. In this study, the focus was on testing and modelling of damage onset and growth under static tensile loading. Two case studies were performed, one in the pristine condition and the other with embedded Teflon inserts

to simulate the effect of pre-existing damage on damage evolution and residual strength. Pulsed thermography and fibre optic sensing systems were used along with strain gauges to validate the finite element models.

2 DESIGN OF THE COMPOSITES JOINT

The composite joint structure, as shown in Fig. 1, was made with unidirectional carbon fibre reinforced polymer (CFRP) composite CYCOM G40-800/5276-1, provided by Cytac Engineered Materials. The monolithic stiffener and the composite skin were fabricated separately in autoclave, and then bonded with AF163-2K structural film adhesive from 3M™. The bondline thickness was controlled within 0.25 ± 0.10 mm. Material mechanical parameters at room temperature ambient conditions are given in Table 1. Recommended cure cycles from the respective material providers were followed.

Fig. 1. Design of bonded composite part attached with steel test fixture

Materials	Parameters at RT condition	Source
CYCOM G40-800/5276-1	$E_{11} = 155$ GPa, $E_{22} = 8.9$ GPa, $G_{12} = G_{13} = 4.8$ GPa, $G_{23} = 2.5$ GPa, and $\nu_{12} = 0.31$ $G_{IC} = 385$ J/m ² , and $G_{IIC} = 700$ N/mm	Technical datasheet of CYCOM 5276-1 toughened epoxy resin
Film adhesive AF163-2K	Bulk parameter: $E_a = 1.1$ GPa, $G_a = 0.41$ GPa, and $\nu_a = 0.34$ $G_{IC} = 2800$ J/m ² , and $G_{IIC} = 4000$ J/m ²	Technical datasheet (November 2009) of 3M Scotch-Weld™ Structural Adhesive Film AF 163-2 NRC internal

Table 1. Material parameters for the bonded laminated composite joint [6,7]

The design of the studied composite part was chosen with reference to the tail boom joint on Cormorant CH-149, a Royal Canadian Air Force (RCAF) search and rescue helicopter. A total of four monolithic carbon fibre reinforced stiffeners are used on the aircraft tail boom section to transfer loads from the tail boom to the fuselage. These joints, each located at a corner position oriented in the longitudinal direction, are bonded and bolted to the composite tail boom on one end, and bolted to a ring interface with the fuselage on the other end. The joint carries mixed loads of mostly tension in the joint longitudinal direction and shear at the stiffener-skin interface.

It is worth noting that although this design has the representative loading features as identified from the actual joint, it is not intended to replicate the actual aircraft component. The case study also does

not properly represent the load distribution in the joint. The goal of this study was to develop an in-house modelling capability for composites structural failure for life management of aircraft structures. A schematic configuration of the fabricated joint with end fixtures is shown in Fig. 1, in which the layup of the 8-ply panel was $[0/45/90/-45]_s$ and the 16-ply stiffener was $[0/45/90/-45]_{2s}$. To study the effect of damage on the performance of bonded joints, two test articles were made of identical material and configuration, one with two circular Teflon inserts of 50.8 mm in diameter under the edges of the stiffener as shown in Fig. 1, and the other one pristine. The Teflon inserts of 0.013 mm in thickness were embedded between the first and second plies of the laminate skin, close to the bondline between the stiffener and the skin panel. The two pivots, at the two fixture ends for linking grips of a test load frame, were approximately 11.5 mm off the panel mid-plane. This specific configuration was determined to ensure high stress concentration at the edges of the stiffener (or the inner end of the bonded overlap). It is anticipated that the damage onset and subsequent failure would occur at the bonded interface and/or in the skin panel in that region. A total of 10 strain gauges were bonded on the stiffener side of the panel to monitor strain in real time at various locations. Each strain gauge measured strain in both the 0° or loading direction of the panel, and the 90° or transverse direction.

3 MECHANICAL TESTING AND DAMAGE GROWTH MEASUREMENT

Mechanical testing was conducted on two test parts – one pristine and one with Teflon inserts – in a MTS hydraulic frame model no. 380.50 with a load cell of 444 kN calibrated to 1% precision traceable to National Standard. The tensile tests were conducted in a controlled displacement mode at a loading rate of 0.254 mm/minute.

Strain distributions were obtained from strain gauges as well as a commercially available Rayleigh backscatter Fibre Optic Sensor (FOS) system provided by Luna Innovations Inc. The strain gauges were mounted on the stiffener side of the panel, and the optical fibre sensors were bonded on the skin side, as shown in Fig. 2. The FOS system uses light backscattered from the imperfections within commonly used telecom fibre to provide strain and temperature measurements over the entire length of the fibre sensor with an equivalent gauge length of 2.6 mm. It consists of a 5 meter long FOS bonded to the skin side of the specimen using AE-10 adhesive and connected to the ODiSI 6000 series interrogator controlled by Luna’s software. The path chosen for the optical fibre installation, shown in Fig. 2, was designed to provide strain response for comparison with the strain gauges, as well as, to witness any changes in the strain due to delamination/disbond propagation between the stiffener and the skin.

Fig. 2: Distributed Fibre Optic Sensor (FOS) location and setup

In addition to the FOS system installed on the skin side, a thermography camera was mounted on the same side to capture damage growth at a regular interval. The pulsed thermography system was equipped with two 2400 J power supplies and Xenon flashes, and an infrared camera with a 20 mK sensitivity in the 8 to 12 μm infrared wavelength. The field of view of the camera covered an area of approximately 100 x 150 mm, centered on the two embedded delamination areas. At each interval, a series of 1800 infrared images were acquired at a rate of 60 frames per second. To obtain damage images, the sequence of infrared images for each series was first processed in the Fourier domain to obtain phase images using pulsed phased thermography [8,9]. These phase images were then subtracted from the baseline image obtained prior to loading (i.e. the first non-null phase image of the series) to generate delamination/disbond images.

4. NUMERICAL MODELLING

Fracture mechanics-based numerical methods have been used to effectively investigate structural performance under various loading conditions [10-17]. In this study, a three-dimensional (3D) FE model including the steel fixture was developed via ABAQUS/CAE, version 2018, as shown in Fig. 3, to predict failure load of the fabricated joint. Through a tie constraint boundary condition, the left fixture was assumed to be a rigid body, tied to the top and bottom skins of the flat panel, and controlled by a “reference point” that was created at one of two designed loading pivot positions. The right side fixture was tied to the stiffener side surfaces, and its far end surfaces were linked to the second “reference point”, located at the second designed pivot position, via a coupling constraint condition. For the part with embedded Teflon inserts, two circular areas of 50.8 mm diameter as shown in Fig. 3(a), were partitioned to the panel top ply to introduce delamination underneath the first ply. The centers of the circular delamination were located at the mid-position of the stiffener inner foot edge. Fig. 3(b) shows the meshed model: the SC8R continuum shell elements for the laminated composite structure, and the C3D8R stress elements for the steel fixtures.

Fig. 3 Three-dimensional finite element model using continuous shell elements and cohesive surface behaviour, where (a) shows the coupon with end fixtures, and (b) is for the meshed model.

Geometrically nonlinear behaviour was considered in this numerical investigation. Also, out-of-plane rotation at the two loading pivots was allowed to simulate the boundary condition in the actual testing. The remaining boundary conditions (BCs) used were: (i) zero displacement in the

three directions and zero rotation in the two directions at the left pivot reference point, 0, and (ii) $U_x = U_y = UR_y = UR_z = 0$ and $U_z = 20$ mm applied at the right pivot reference point.

Through previous testing of a pristine coupon, it was noticed that a major failure mode was delamination in the top ply in the inner panel-stiffener overlap end region; very limited cohesion failure was observed at the bond interface. Therefore, the tie constraint condition was then further used to attach the stiffener and the panel without including the actual adhesive layer. The cohesive behaviour technique was used to “attach” the two top ply strips to the remaining panel, in which the “node to surface” discretization method and the BK law were used to model damage onset and evolution [18-23]. The failure criteria were: (1) stiffness of 4×10^4 N/mm for K_{nn} , K_{ss} , and K_{tt} , (ii) damage onset with maximum nominal stress of 30 MPa for three fracture modes, (iii) damage evolution with fracture energy of 1.2 N/mm for all three modes.

5. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

5.1 Experimental results of damage evolution and failure

Fig. 4 (a) shows the measured tensile load and the crosshead displacement of the test frame of the two test panels, subjected to tensile loading at the room temperature ambient environment. The test results show that there was an initial out-of-plane bending at the start of the test due to alignment of fixture and test part. This was followed by an elastic region where the load increased linearly with the displacement under tensile loading, until skin and stiffener separation occurred as signified by drop in load. Fig. 4(b) shows the failure modes of the two test panels, where the pristine panel failed in a mixed laminate/cohesion mode, the pre-delaminated panel failed in the skin laminate only. The ultimate failure loads also the peak loads were defined by the load at which total separation was observed between the skin and the stiffener. The ultimate failure loads were 85.7 kN and 94.1 kN for the pristine and pre-delaminated panels respectively. Within the scatter, there was no significant difference in ultimate strengths of the panels with or without embedded Teflon. This is mainly due to the fact that while delamination onset may be affected by the presence of pre-existing damage, the peak strength was determined mostly by fibre breakage to allow detachment of the stiffener from the skin at the interface of the first and second plies.

(a)

(b) pristine (left); with embedded Teflon (right)

Fig. 4 (a) Measured load and load frame displacement during tensile testing of bonded composite panels, and (b) failure modes. Thermography images were taken at regular unloading/reloading intervals on the panel with Teflon inserts.

Fig. 5 Measured strain along optical fibre Segment B

Fig. 6 Thermography images showing delamination growth during tensile testing

Fig. 5 shows the strain measurements of Segment B (left bond) under different loading conditions by the FOS, where the locations of delamination edges along the longitudinal direction were marked by two valleys highlighted with two curves on the graph. The distance between the two curves at any given load represents the measured delamination length. Thermography images in Fig. 6 illustrated the detected damage growth of the two embedded delamination areas during testing, with the left blue image referring to delamination under the left skin/stiffener bond, and right image representing that under the right bond.

The correlations of damage lengths from the two damage monitoring approaches – the FOS and thermography – along Segments B and D are shown in Fig. 7(a) and (b) respectively. A consistent trend of damage growth was observed using both methods, where damage grew sooner along the skin/stiffener of Segment B, than that of Segment D. As compared to the FOS, thermography appears to underestimate the damage growth. The initial Teflon size of 50.8 mm was correctly detected by the FOS, but the thermography images revealed a smaller damage size. Thermography yielded closer results with the FOS as the damage grew larger along Segment B, though it failed to capture the event of sudden damage growth along Segment D upon final part failure with total separation. It is well known that thermography may not detect damage when close physical contact remains. Due to heat diffusion, the deeper the damage, the larger discontinuity from the thermography. In comparison, the FOS, a well-proven strain-mapping approach, demonstrated its ability to detect damage growth in composites. However, more study is needed to establish the fidelity and sensitivity of this approach.

Fig. 7 Comparison of damage growth characterized by Luna fibre optic system and thermography at optical fibre Segment B (a) and Segment D (b)

5.2 FEA model validation

Damage onset and evolution, as well as the resulting progressive failure behaviour, were assessed numerically. The failure was predicted to be the peak load, at which point the model was aborted due to a numerical convergence issue with excessive large delamination. The predicted failure forces were approximately 96.9 kN for the pristine model, and 89.2 kN for the model with Teflon inserts. The relative difference of the predicted 96.9 kN and the tested 85.7kN was approximately 13% for the pristine panel. The difference was 4% for the panel with pre-existing damage, where a peak load of 89.2 kN was obtained from prediction and 85.7 kN from testing.

A good correlation in the delamination growth curves was obtained between the experimental and numerical results as shown in Fig. 8. It should be noted that the current FEA model cannot capture unsymmetrical damage progression in the two bonded stiffener and skin zones, and such correlation only applies to the Segment B with the earlier damage growth. The numerical model shows that no damage growth was observed until a specific tensile load was reached, approximately 65 kN for the pre-delaminated case, and 85 kN for the pristine one. Such a difference suggests that pre-existing damage could reduce the load carrying capability of the structure, posing a higher risk of part failure. It should be noted that the effect of damage is highly dependent on the size and location of the damage, as well as the load spectrum of the structures, amongst other factors. This study demonstrates that the investigated bonded composite structure was highly damage tolerant where no damage growth occurred, with or without pre-existing delamination, until the load close to the ultimate value was reached. At the same time, once the damage started growing, it propagated quickly with increase in loading until final failure.

Fig. 9 shows the predicted failure mode of the studied bonded composite joint - laminate failure for both pristine and the pre-delaminated panels. As shown in Table 1, fracture toughness G_{IC} and G_{IIC} , of 5276-1, the matrix in the laminate is significantly weaker than that of the adhesive AF163-2K. This predicted failure mode correlates well with the experiment for the case of the panel with embedded Teflon inserts, where the artificial delamination continued to grow in the skin laminate. For the pristine panel, damage onset could occur in both the adhesive bondline and within the laminate due to stress concentration around the edges of the skin and stiffener bonds. Under predominately Mode II shear load in this test, damage was prone to propagate mostly in the skin laminate due to its weaker fracture toughness, as observed in the testing result; however, the damage onset in the bondline could also remain as observed in the experiment. Further study is needed to focus on the prediction of damage onset and propagation for the pristine case.

Fig. 8 Comparison of the delamination growth along Segment B obtained from the Luna fibre optic system, thermography, and numerical methods.

Fig. 9 Predicted failure mode in the panel skin ply (deformation was enlarged by 10 times).

5.3 Strain comparison

As shown in Fig. 10, a comparison of strain measurements for the test panel with Teflon inserts shows consistent results from the strain gauge, the FOS sensors, as well as prediction during the entire tests at S5, the location on the top of the skin panel as marked in Fig. 2. The good match demonstrates the reliability of the FOS for strain measurements, and offers a base for model validation.

Good agreement in the strain variation was also obtained between the experimental and numerical results on the critical locations of the pristine test panel. Fig. 11 shows the strain comparisons at selected locations for model validation. The strain gauge reading E on top of the stiffener panel close to strain gauge F (on skin panel) was erratic towards the end of the test. The erratic strain reading was driven by the progressive separation of the bond interface on which the strain gauge was mounted.

Fig. 10 Comparison of strain measurements from strain gauge (SG5), fibre optic system and prediction at far field location of S5 of the test panel with embedded Teflon inserts

Fig. 11 Measured and predicted strains at locations B, E F for the pristine panel

6. CONCLUSION

Life management of composite structures by relying more on prediction and less on large and full-scale testing is a way to reduce downtime and maintenance costs. This work focus on model development to predict damage tolerance of a bonded composite joint under tensile loading. A finite element model was developed with incorporation of cohesive zone behaviour developed via ABAQUS/CAE code to evaluate the effect of pre-existing damage, generated by embedded Teflon inserts, in critical locations on loading carrying capability of the bonded joint. The numerical modelling was able to predict damage onset and final failure, with good correlation of damage growth as detected via experimental methods, including pulsed thermography and a backscatter fibre optic sensor system.

The experimental and modelling results show that the bonded composite structure used in this study is highly damage tolerant. In spite of the embedded Teflon inserts of 50.8 mm in diameter at critical locations, the damages did not grow until the load was close to the ultimate value for the structures. It did show that embedded delaminations reduced the load carrying capability, at which point the damage started to propagate. The failure modes of both pristine and pre-delaminated panels show that under predominately Mode II shear load at the skin and stiffener interface, the main failure mode was laminate failure, although mixed laminate/cohesion failure was observed in the pristine test panel.

This work demonstrates that a fibre optic sensing system is not only a reliable method for strain-mapping, it also offers great potential for damage growth monitoring. Pulsed thermography and a backscatter fibre optic sensor were employed in this study to provide damage growth monitoring. Pulsed thermography technique and fibre optic systems correlated well with each other as a mean of capturing the occurrences of damage onset and propagation, though thermography tends to underestimate the damage size.

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